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Obesity Surgery

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Dear Editor,

The recent surge in obesity surgery, particularly its application to individuals with lower Body Mass Indexes (BMIs), has sparked both hope and controversy. While it's undeniable that surgery can offer significant weight loss and health improvements for some, I write to advocate for a balanced perspective and highlight the need for holistic care beyond the scalpel (1-3).

Firstly, the decision for surgery should never be considered lightly. Comprehensive lifestyle interventions, including healthy diet, regular exercise, and addressing underlying psychological factors, must be prioritised for all patients, regardless of BMI. Surgery should be reserved for individuals who have exhausted non-surgical approaches or for those with severe obesity-related comorbidities significantly impacting their quality of life. Secondly, the current emphasis on BMI as the sole criterion for bariatric surgery is an oversimplification. Body composition, metabolic health, and individual needs should be meticulously evaluated. Focusing solely on a number risks overlooking significant variations in patients' health profiles and potentially denying eligible individuals who might benefit from surgery, while also subjecting others to unnecessary risks (4-7).

Thirdly, bariatric surgery is not a magic bullet. It requires significant post-operative lifestyle modifications and long-term commitment to maintain weight loss and health gains. Patients need robust support systems, including nutritional counselling, psychological therapy, and physical activity guidance, to navigate the long-term journey towards sustained health. Finally, we must acknowledge the potential psychological toll of surgery. Body image struggles, eating disorders, and depression can arise. Therefore, pre- and post-operative mental health assessments and interventions are crucial (5-7).

In conclusion, while obesity surgery can be a valuable tool, it should be employed with caution, after rigorous evaluation, and within a framework of holistic care that prioritizes long-term physical and mental well-being. Let us shift our focus from the

quick fix of a scalpel to empowering individuals with the knowledge and support needed to cultivate sustainable healthy lifestyles.

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